

KALEIDOS PROJECT
Creating synergies for research
knowledge valorisation

**D1.2 Modular training program for researchers: KALEIDOS
Ideas Generation Programme**

Grant No: 101132079

Start date: 01.02.2024

Duration: 36 months

Project website: <https://kaleidosproject.eu>

DELIVERABLE REPORT	
Deliverable No.	D1.2
Deliverable Name	Modular training programme for researchers: KALEIDOS Ideas Generation Programme
Version No.	V3
Responsible partner	UAB
Lead Authors (Name; email)	Begoña Miñarro, begona.minarro@uab.cat ; Sofia Mojica Baquero sofia.mojica@uab.cat ; Meritxell Cardús, meritxell.cardus@uab.cat
Due date of deliverable (DD/MM/YYYY)	30/09/2025
Actual deliverable date (DD/MM/YYYY)	30/09/2025
Justification if delayed	N/A

**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the European Union under grant agreement n° 101132079

DISSEMINATION LEVEL OF THIS REPORT (PLEASE INDICATE):

PU	Public – fully open	X
SEN	Sensitive – limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

	KALEIDOS CONSORTIUM	Acronym	Role	Country	Org type
1	WEDO PROJECT INTELLIGENCE MADE EASYSL ¹	WeDo	COO	ES	SME
2	UNIVERSITAT AUTONOMA DE BARCELONA	UAB	BEN	ES	RTD
2.1	FUNDACIO PRIVADA PARC DE RECERCA UAB	PRUAB	AE	ES	RTD
3	ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA	UNIBO	BEN	IT	RTD
4	KARLSTADS UNIVERSITET	KU	BEN	SE	RTD
5	UNIVERSITE DE LORRAINE	UL	BEN	FR	RTD
6	UNIVERSITY OF HAIFA	UH	BEN	IL	RTD

***Legend** = Role in the Project: **C** – Coordinator // **B** – Beneficiary // **AP** – Associated Partner // Organization Type: **RTD** – Research and Technological Development // **PHI** – Public Health Institution // **Hosp** – Hospital // **SME** – Small and medium-sized enterprises. // **LC** – Large Company // **NGO** – Non-Governmental Org.

¹ Project Coordinator

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or other granting authorities. Neither the European Union nor the granting authorities can be held responsible for them.

Authors List

Lead Authors		
Name	Beneficiary	Email
Begoña Miñarro Vivas	UAB	begona.minarro@uab.cat
Sofía Mojica Baquero	UAB	sofia.mojica@uab.cat
Meritxell Cardús	PrUAB	meritxell.cardus@uab.cat

Version Control

Version	Description	Partner	Date
V1	First draft	UAB	Jul. 15 th , 2025
V2	Review	KAU, UNIBO, WeDo	Aug. 20 th , 2025
V3	Consolidation and final version	UAB	Sep. 29 th , 2025

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
EC	European Commission
WP	Work Package

Table of Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
INTRODUCTION	5
DESIGNING THE KALEIDOS IDEAS GENERATION PROGRAMME	6
PREPARATORY STEPS.....	6
STRUCTURE OF THE PROGRAMME	7
GENERAL OBJECTIVES OF THE PROGRAMME	7
ACTORS INVOLVED IN THE PROCESS	7
CONTENT OF THE KALEIDOS IDEAS GENERATION PROGRAMME	8
A.1 PARTICIPATIVE AND CREATIVE PROCESS: CHALLENGE IDENTIFICATION, PROBLEM FRAMING / FRAMING PITCH / UX TRAINING	8
A.2 SOLUTION BRAINSTORMING/IMPACT, FEASIBILITY SOLUTION EVALUATION AND SELECTION / MENTORS FEEDBACK.....	12
A.3 LEADERSHIP, TEAMWORK AND VALUES TRAINING	15
A.4 LEAN STARTUP METHODOLOGIES	18
A.5 OPEN SCIENCE AND KNOWLEDGE VALORISATION	22
A.6 INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY.....	25
A.7 DIGITAL RESOURCES TO CREATE HIGH-IMPACT VISUAL PRESENTATIONS FOR YOUR PROJECTS & ELEVATOR PITCH TRAINING.....	28
A.8 COMMUNICATION TO GENERAL PUBLIC	31
A.9 RESOURCES AND FINANCIAL CHALLENGES	34
A.10 MENTORING.....	36
A.11 PROTOTYPING	39
A.12 FINAL PRESENTATION SIMULATION	41
A.13 FINAL EVENT	43
CONCLUSION	46
ANNEX 1. RESEARCHERS' TEAMS.....	48

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

PARTICIPATIVE & CO-CREATIVE PROCESSES

The starting point for the program is the challenge identified by ecosystem stakeholders and the goal of the program is to find possible ideas for solutions that could tackle this challenge. In this first sessions, **participants work in group dynamics collaborating with stakeholders that have proposed the challenges**, in order to better understand their needs and be able to provide a more complete response to the challenge.

ONLINE TRAINING

- Leadership, teamwork and values training
- Lean startup methodologies
- Open Science and Knowledge Valorization
- Intellectual Property
- Digital resources to create high-impact visual presentations for your projects + Elevator pitch training
- Communication to General Public
- Resources and financial challenges
- Final presentation simulation

MENTORING

In the timeframe of the program, there participants have the opportunity for mentoring sessions. **The mentor is a person selected based on the challenge that can provide expert advise in the definition of the solutions and the development of the ideas.**

PROTOTYPING

This session focuses on **providing participants help with prototyping, project design and presentation of the solution project.**

FINAL EVENT

The projects present their **solutions** and define the next steps to consolidate them in a project idea.

The KALEIDOS Ideas Generation Programme is the result of a collaborative effort between UAB, PRUAB, UL, KAU, and WeDo. It was designed to create an innovative training programme based on the existing best practices in knowledge valorisation at these institutions, with the aim of empowering researchers to address regional societal challenges.

Figure 1. Overview of the KALEIDOS Idea Generation Program

INTRODUCTION

The Deliverable 1.2 “Modular training for researchers: KALEIDOS Ideas Generation Programme” includes the objectives, materials, and exercises for the online sessions carried out within the KALEIDOS Ideas Generation Programme. It builds upon the selected Open Science Skills for researchers in the Deliverable 1.1 Analysis and Portfolio of professional skills and competences for Open Science and the existing Knowledge Valorisation Best Practices of the consortium partners.

The deliverable is structured with the following sections: Designing the KALEIDOS Ideas Generation Programme; Content of the KALEIDOS Ideas Generation Programme; and Conclusions.

DESIGNING THE KALEIDOS IDEAS GENERATION PROGRAMME

The KALEIDOS Ideas Generation Programme is the result of a collaborative effort between UAB, PRUAB, UL, KAU, and WeDo. It was designed to create an innovative training programme based on the existing best practices in knowledge valorisation at these institutions, with the aim of empowering researchers to address regional societal challenges:

- KVBP-1 – Ideas Generation Programme
- KVBP-3 – Connection STEM and SSH for multidisciplinary teams
- KVBP-4 – Training of values
- KVBP-5 - Training on EC Horizon Europe proposal submission, Open science and Impact
- KVBP-6 - Innovation training

The design of the programme allowed KALEIDOS partners to adapt and enrich their own existing models. Rather than replacing institutional or personal practices, the programme emphasised integration, reflection, and the adoption of complementary tools where relevant.

Preparatory steps

Before the launch of the training programme, several key preparatory steps were undertaken:

- Agreement among KALEIDOS partners on the overarching thematic focus of the programme: ageing as a major regional challenge.
- Mapping and identification of relevant regional stakeholder networks related to ageing in each participating region.
- Alignment and integration of existing knowledge valorisation practices from each institution to design a coherent and context-sensitive training pathway.
- Organisation of challenge identification workshops in each region to define specific sub-challenges within the broader theme of ageing.
- Definition of selection criteria for researchers eligible to participate in the programme.
- Selection of researchers to take part in the initiative.
- Identification of regional mentors, who would guide and support research teams in the development of their ideas.

Structure of the programme

The [KALEIDOS Ideas Generation programme](#) consisted of the following core components:

- Participative and Creative Process: Two interactive sessions of three hours each, aimed at helping researchers identify impactful and feasible solutions to the identified regional sub-challenges.
- Training Sessions: A series of 9 sessions focused on developing key transversal skills—such as innovation, communication, stakeholder engagement, and impact assessment—needed to transform research outcomes into actionable, real-world solutions.
- Mentoring: Each regional team was paired with one or more mentors, who provided ongoing guidance and feedback throughout the development of their ideas.
- Final Presentation: Each team had the opportunity to present their ideas, sharing their proposed solutions with peers, mentors, and stakeholders.

General objectives of the programme

The primary objectives of the KALEIDOS Ideas Generation Programme were to:

- Involve researchers in addressing regional societal challenges through knowledge valorisation.
- Facilitate the transfer of research-based knowledge into practical solutions.
- Help researchers acquire transferable skills relevant to both academic and non-academic career paths.
- Encourage participants to adapt and extend their own models and practices by engaging with new approaches from across the consortium.

Actors involved in the process

Regarding the actors involved, both in the previous stages of the launch of the programme and during its implementation:

- Regional stakeholders played a key role in identifying the challenges addressed by the programme.
- A total of six trainers were engaged in delivering the training modules.
- Six mentors were involved in guiding the regional research teams through the mentoring sessions.
- This pilot edition of the KALEIDOS Ideas Generation Programme, involving UAB, UL, KAU, and UNIBO, successfully engaged twenty researchers across the participating institutions. The researchers' teams, with their mentors, can be consulted in Annex 1.

CONTENT OF THE KALEIDOS IDEAS GENERATION PROGRAMME

A.1 Participative and creative process: Challenge identification, problem framing / framing pitch / UX training

Background and context

This session is part of the broader framework of the KALEIDOS project, which supports universities in their transition toward an innovation management model grounded in Open Science principles. It was designed to address the growing need for participatory knowledge valorisation practices that can respond to systemic societal challenges, with a special focus on ageing, the central theme of this workshop.

Ageing is a complex and multifaceted issue that requires user-centred and ecosystem-aware approaches. It encompasses challenges related to health, inclusion, economic resilience, and technological adaptation. KALEIDOS tackles this by placing quadruple-helix collaboration—academia, public sector, industry, and civil society—at the core of its ideation, innovation, and training processes.

By using ageing as a thematic anchor and participatory design as the core methodology, this session contributed to the creation of practical, inclusive, and ecosystem-based solutions, reinforcing the overall mission of KALEIDOS to foster social impact through research valorisation.

Objective

This hands-on session, part of the KALEIDOS training, aimed to introduce participatory, user-centred innovation methods; build competences in Open Science and knowledge valorisation; and foster the co-creation of innovative, feasible, and socially relevant solutions to address ageing-related challenges.

Target audience

Early-stage and experienced researchers, innovation managers, and academic professionals from universities and research institutions involved in knowledge valorisation.

Methodology and content

The session followed an experiential and participatory methodology, rooted in co-creation and user-centred innovation principles. The training was structured around

collaborative group work, blending theoretical insights with interactive exercises to foster critical thinking, creativity, and real-world problem solving.

Participants began by identifying and framing challenges related to ageing. The session opened with an introduction to problem framing, underlining its importance in clarifying complex societal issues. Several methods and tools were introduced to guide the process:

- Stakeholder and empathy mapping to visualise the needs, expectations, and tensions of all actors involved.
- The "five whys" technique to explore root causes beyond superficial symptoms.
- The "how might we" (HMW) method to transform insights into open, actionable questions that can inspire innovation.

Participants then worked in multidisciplinary teams within virtual breakout rooms to explore potential solutions. This phase included a brainstorming session, where they could contribute both new ideas and ongoing projects relevant to the ageing challenge. Next came analysis and voting, helping teams to prioritise the most promising ideas based on technical feasibility, user needs, and innovation potential.

Once selected, ideas underwent a benchmarking exercise, where participants examined existing solutions in the field of ageing to identify differentiation opportunities and refine their concepts.

The session concluded with a collective sharing space, in which teams presented their proposals and received feedback through a "social rain" of contributions from peers and facilitators.

This approach ensured that participants not only gained practical tools and collaborative techniques, but also internalised a mindset of mission-oriented, socially impactful innovation.

Materials needed

The session was designed to be adaptable to both online and face-to-face formats, with a set of tools and materials tailored to foster participation, creativity, and collaboration in each context. The [slides used during the session 1](#) can be found on the KALEIDOS website.

For Face-to-Face Sessions

- Sticky notes and flip charts for stakeholder mapping, empathy maps, idea clustering, and voting.
- Markers, pens, coloured dots or stickers for visual ideation and prioritisation activities.
- Printed templates for exercises
- Projector or screen for presenting theoretical content and guiding instructions.

For Online Sessions

- Videoconferencing platform with breakout room functionality (e.g., Zoom, MS Teams) to enable small group work.
- Digital whiteboards (e.g., Miro, Mural, Jamboard) for stakeholder mapping, idea clustering, and interactive brainstorming.

- Shared cloud-based documents or slides (e.g., Google Docs, Slides) to document group outputs and facilitate collaboration.
- Screen sharing and chat functions to support facilitator-led instruction and peer interaction.

Common Materials for Both Formats

- Facilitation guidelines and exercise templates, adapted to each dynamic.
- Access to internet-connected devices (laptops or tablets).
- Benchmarking resources, including example links or datasets for online research on existing solutions.
- Session agenda and challenge briefing documents to align participants with goals and context.

Exercises for face-to-face and online sessions

All exercises implemented during the session were designed to be flexible and fully adaptable to both in-person and online environments, ensuring consistent learning outcomes regardless of format. Each activity was structured to facilitate active participation, collaboration, and the co-creation of knowledge, whether through physical materials in a room or digital tools in virtual spaces.

- **Idea brainstorming**
Teams generate a wide range of solution ideas—new or existing—responding to the selected HMW questions.
- **Idea clustering and prioritisation**
Teams group, analyse, and vote on the most promising ones based on feasibility, innovation potential, and user relevance.
- **Benchmarking activity**
Participants research similar initiatives or existing solutions in the field of ageing to assess uniqueness and added value of their own ideas.
- **Social rain of contributions**
Final presentation and feedback round where each team shares its proposal and receives comments, questions, and suggestions from other groups and facilitators.

Outcomes of the session and skills and competences addressed

As a result of the first KALEIDOS co-creation session on the challenge of ageing, participants developed and shared a set of initial innovation proposals. These emerged through collaborative problem framing, stakeholder analysis, and brainstorming activities conducted in multidisciplinary teams. The proposals reflect context-specific insights from each participating institution and demonstrate alignment with the principles of Open Science and mission-driven innovation.

Key Outcomes by Partner:

- Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona: Proposal for developing digital tools (apps, smart panels) tailored to older adults, in collaboration with local networks, to improve access to essential services (e.g., healthcare, shopping, social spaces) through small-scale, user-friendly transport solutions.
- Université de Lorraine: Proposals focused on digital inclusion and empowerment of older people:
 - Partnerships with local governments and educational institutions to provide digital literacy training and cybersecurity awareness.
 - Development of simplified user interfaces supported by integrated audio chatbots to facilitate technology adoption.
- Karlstad University: A reflective proposal questioning how to enhance digital health tools to better serve ageing populations:
 - Emphasis on digital literacy barriers, cost-effectiveness, and the risk of social exclusion.
 - Strategic questions raised on balancing technological innovation with social connection and inclusivity.
- Università di Bologna: Proposal to map and connect regional initiatives in the Emilia-Romagna region:
 - Creation of a project platform to showcase ageing-related innovation.
 - Design of a matchmaking app to link stakeholders, solutions, and opportunities.

Throughout the session, participants developed competences identified in the D1.1 skills portfolio, including:

- **Systemic thinking** - Participants explored challenges such as ageing by mapping interrelated causes, actors, and structures across societal ecosystems.
- **Critical thinking** - The “5 Whys” and stakeholder analysis techniques helped participants examine underlying causes, not just visible symptoms.
- **Strategic thinking** - Participants aligned problem framing with high-impact areas and realistic innovation opportunities.
- **Empathy** - Empathy mapping encouraged a user-centred mindset, highlighting the needs, motivations, and tensions of affected groups.
- **Creativity** - Through open-ended reframing methods like “How Might We...?”, teams generated novel ways to approach social challenges.
- **Promote open innovation** - The co-creation format reflected quadruple helix collaboration and the early inclusion of diverse perspectives in innovation processes.
- **Interact professionally** - Participants practiced active listening, consensus-building, and respectful idea exchange in team settings.
- **Work in teams** - Small-group exercises fostered shared problem analysis, idea development, and co-responsibility—essential for interdisciplinary collaboration.

- **Conduct interdisciplinary research** – Team members took the first steps to be able to address societal challenges by conducting interdisciplinary research.

A.2 Solution brainstorming/Impact, Feasibility solution evaluation and selection / Mentors feedback

Background and context

This session builds on the previous challenge-framing workshop and forms part of the KALEIDOS Ideas Generation Programme, which guides participants through the complete cycle of co-creation—from problem definition to solution development.

Objective

To support participants in transforming initial ideas into validated, feasible, and impactful innovation proposals through collaborative brainstorming, technical and strategic evaluation, and early-stage prototyping.

Target audience

Early-stage and experienced researchers, innovation managers, and academic professionals from universities and research institutions involved in knowledge valorisation.

Methodology and content

This session followed a structured, collaborative methodology inspired by design thinking, guiding participants from the initial solution proposals developed in Session 1 toward impactful, feasible, and user-oriented innovation concepts. The process was divided into a series of progressive phases, each supported by visual templates and co-creation tools to facilitate team alignment and idea development.

The core methodology combined team-based ideation, peer review, benchmarking, and early-stage prototyping:

- **1. Reframing and developing initial proposals**

Starting from the ideas generated in the previous session, teams used the *Initial Project Folder* template—a colourful, visual canvas—to structure their proposals. This included:

- Definition of the core problem
- Analysis of current solutions
- Articulation of the team’s unique idea and initial branding
- Identification of added value, technological basis, and potential market
- Mapping of strategic partnerships and potential funding channels

This structured canvas helped standardise team outputs and made innovation elements visible and comparable.

- **2. Visual prototyping**

Teams created low-fidelity prototypes using a variety of formats:

- Iconographic sketches
- Infographic designs
- AI-generated visual elements
- Basic app or web mock-ups

The use of pre-designed visual templates encouraged experimentation and creativity, regardless of participants' design experience.

- **3. Group presentation and feedback**

Each group presented their idea and prototype in a central plenary session. Participants provided quick and constructive feedback using the “social rain” method. In addition, mentors and facilitators offered strategic guidance to refine proposals and identify paths forward.

This methodology ensured that participants not only explored their ideas conceptually but also translated them into tangible, communicable formats, gaining critical insights into their feasibility, potential impact, and alignment with ecosystem needs.

Materials needed

As with the previous session, this workshop was designed to be fully adaptable to both online and face-to-face formats, ensuring consistency in participant engagement and learning outcomes regardless of the delivery setting. The [slides used during session 2](#) can be found on the KALEIDOS website.

To support the collaborative and creative nature of the session, the following materials were used:

- Initial project folder templates (digital or printed), including sections for problem definition, value proposition, technology, partnerships, and funding.
- Visual prototyping resources, such as icon sets, infographic elements, sketching tools, or mock-up generators.
- Facilitation slides and guiding questions, to structure team discussions and maintain session flow.

Whether in person or online, the setup promoted active teamwork, creativity and strategic thinking, with materials that were simple, visual, and intuitive to use.

Exercises for face-to-face and online sessions

The exercises in this session were carefully designed to be fully adaptable to both face-to-face and online delivery, ensuring that all participants could engage meaningfully in the innovation process regardless of the format. Activities were structured to promote collaborative thinking, visual synthesis, evaluation, and prototyping, using shared templates and facilitation tools.

1. Project framing with the initial project folder

Each team worked with a structured visual template to define and articulate their innovation proposal. This canvas guided participants through key aspects such as

- Problem definition and current solutions
- Proposal description and added value

- Technologies used, potential users, and funding opportunities
- Strategic partnerships and next steps

2. Visual prototyping

Each team produced a low-fidelity prototype of their selected idea. Formats included:

- Iconographic sketches or infographics
- App or web mock-ups
- AI-generated visuals or concept videos

3. Collective sharing and mentors' feedback

Teams presented their ideas and visual prototypes in a central plenary session.

Participants offered peer input through a "social rain of contributions", while mentors provided expert guidance for refinement.

Outcomes of the session and skills and competences addressed

This session enabled the maturation and visual prototyping of selected innovation ideas, building on the proposals generated in Session 1. Through a collaborative process of refinement, evaluation, and feedback, participants transformed early-stage concepts into structured, feasible, and impactful solutions, supported by clear value propositions and preliminary visual representations.

Key Outcomes

- Selection and consolidation of one innovation idea per team.
- Completion of the "Initial Project Folder" template, covering key elements such as problem framing, technological foundation, stakeholder engagement, added value, and funding pathways.
- Development of initial prototypes using visual tools, graphic sketches, and basic app/web mock-ups.

Skills and Competences Addressed

The session directly contributed to the development of several transversal and role-specific competences identified in the D1.1, including:

- **Creativity** - Participants used divergent thinking to expand on initial ideas, applying brainstorming and ideation tools to generate multiple innovative solutions.
- **Strategic thinking** - Through feasibility and impact assessments, teams identified which ideas aligned best with user needs, resources, and societal value.
- **Critical thinking** - Peer and mentor feedback challenged assumptions, leading participants to refine, combine, or discard ideas based on evidence and relevance.
- **Decision making** - Teams selected their final idea using weighted criteria, balancing desirability, viability, and technical feasibility.

- **Interact professionally** - The session fostered respectful collaboration, peer evaluation, and constructive interaction with mentors in an interdisciplinary context.
- **Work in teams** - Participants co-developed ideas in small groups, negotiated direction, and achieved consensus around shared innovation goals.
- **Conduct interdisciplinary research** – Team members took the first steps to be able to address societal challenges by conducting interdisciplinary research.
- **Increase impact of science on policy and society** - Evaluation criteria explicitly addressed potential social benefit, aligning solutions with broader mission-oriented innovation principles.
- **Empathy** - Solutions were assessed through the lens of real user challenges, requiring participants to remain attentive to stakeholder perspectives.

This session reinforced participants' capacity to act as agents of change within their institutions and regional environments, in line with the KALEIDOS mission to promote Open Science-based innovation.

A.3 Leadership, teamwork and values training

Background and context

This session forms part of the broader KALEIDOS training programme and focuses on developing the personal and interpersonal competences essential for effective co-creation and collaboration within research and innovation environments. While less participatory than other modules, the session offers a reflective and structured space to explore leadership, teamwork dynamics, and the role of shared values in interdisciplinary settings.

By addressing the human factors behind successful innovation, this session strengthens the collaborative foundation of the KALEIDOS experience.

Objective

To foster researchers' ability to lead and collaborate effectively by exploring personal and group values, understanding team dynamics and conflict styles, and co-creating shared commitments. The session aims to build the emotional intelligence, reflection, and interpersonal awareness needed to manage collaboration and decision-making in Open Science-based innovation environments.

Target audience

Researchers, project leaders, and innovation professionals working in multidisciplinary teams or involved in co-creation, collaboration, or Open Science-based innovation.

Methodology and content

The session combined short presentations, individual reflection, and group dialogue to address the interpersonal and intrapersonal dimensions of teamwork in Open Science contexts. It was structured around the following modules:

- **Introduction:** Setting the tone with big-picture questions about leadership and collaboration. Participants were invited to reflect on common team dysfunctions and red flags, such as unclear roles, lack of trust, or value misalignment.
- **Learning styles inventory:** Using Kolb's experiential learning framework, participants identified their learning styles (Accommodator, Diverger, Converger, Assimilator) and explored how these preferences influence how they lead, follow, and communicate within a team.
- **Values and value-based action:** This block focused on recognising and prioritising personal and group values, and translating them into committed action:
 - How to act consistently with one's values in team settings
 - How to manage value conflicts when collaboration challenges individual convictions
 - Collaborative activity to define the team's top five priorities as a shared reference
- **Conflict management:** Introduction to the Thomas-Kilmann Conflict Mode Instrument, allowing participants to self-assess their dominant conflict-handling style (e.g., avoiding, accommodating, competing, compromising, collaborating) and reflect on the implications for group dynamics.
- **Wrap-up and reflection:** A final plenary moment was used to share insights and consolidate key learning. Teams reflected on what they would carry forward into their collaborative innovation processes.

The overall format supported self-awareness, peer learning, and stronger interpersonal foundations for co-creation. While less participatory than previous sessions, this module created the relational groundwork needed for mission-oriented, interdisciplinary teamwork.

Materials needed

The session required a limited but targeted set of materials to support reflection, self-assessment, and group discussion. These included:

- Presentation slides introducing theoretical frameworks and guiding questions
- Learning Styles Inventory (Kolb model – digital or printed questionnaire)
- Thomas-Kilmann Conflict Mode Instrument (for individual self-assessment)
- Team Values Prioritisation Template, for identifying and agreeing on shared principles
- Digital whiteboard or physical flipcharts for group discussions and visual capture

- Note-taking tools or personal reflection journals (optional)

The [slides used during session 3](#) can be found on the KALEIDOS website.

Exercises for face-to-face and online sessions

Although this session was more reflective and less participatory than previous ones, it still integrated several interactive exercises designed to promote self-awareness, group dialogue, and shared value-building. All activities were easily adaptable for both in-person and online delivery formats.

1. Leadership & teamwork warm-up

Participants responded to reflective prompts such as:

- “What makes a team fail or thrive?”
- “What signals tell us a team is not working well?”

These questions helped surface assumptions and stimulate discussion.

2. Kolb learning styles self-assessment

Using a brief questionnaire, participants identified their dominant learning style. Results were then discussed in small groups to explore how team diversity affects collaboration.

3. Thomas-Kilmann conflict style exercise

Each participant completed the conflict-handling style inventory and reflected on its implications for teamwork.

4. Team values prioritisation

In teams, participants listed, discussed, and prioritised shared values, eventually selecting the top five values that would guide their collaboration.

5. Co-creation of a commitment statement

Each team developed a brief values-based commitment statement, synthesising what they expect from each other and how they aim to work together going forward.

Outcomes of the session and skills and competences addressed

This session resulted in the reinforcement of key interpersonal skills and shared team alignment, creating the relational foundation necessary for sustained collaboration in Open Science-based innovation projects. Though less hands-on than previous workshops, the session facilitated deep reflection on how individuals function within teams, how to manage differences, and how to articulate shared values and commitments.

Key Outcomes

- Increased self-awareness of participants’ leadership styles, learning preferences, and conflict management approaches.

- Strengthened understanding of team roles, dysfunctions, and behavioural signals.
- Identification and prioritisation of shared team values, supporting alignment in collaborative work.
- Co-creation of team commitment statements, translating values into behavioural principles.

Skills and Competences Addressed

The session contributed to the development of several key transversal and interpersonal competences highlighted in the KALEIDOS D1.1 skills portfolio, including:

- **Interact professionally** - Participants practiced respectful and constructive engagement within teams, reflecting on communication, collaboration, and responsibility.
- **Work in teams** - A core focus of the session, participants explored group dynamics, learned how to build shared values, and worked toward collective decision-making.
- **Conduct interdisciplinary research** – Participants got relevant insights to enhance the process of developing an idea in an interdisciplinary team
- **Strategic thinking** - Through leadership reflection and team alignment exercises, participants developed strategies for setting shared priorities and navigating conflicts.
- **Empathy** - Understanding team members' perspectives and values was essential to fostering cohesion, inclusion, and psychological safety.
- **Self-regulation** - Participants explored how to manage personal values and emotions in collaborative settings, particularly when conflicts arise.
- **Critical thinking** - Teams were encouraged to critically analyse leadership models, group behaviour, and the alignment (or misalignment) between values and actions.
- **Valuing sustainability** - Participants were invited to define the values that would guide their team's innovation work over time, reinforcing sustainable collaboration.
- **Decision making** - Exercises around value prioritisation and leadership scenarios promoted thoughtful, inclusive decision-making processes.

A.4 Lean startup methodologies

Background and context

This session represents a key transition in the KALEIDOS training programme—from idea generation to early-stage business modelling—and forms an essential part of the Ideas Generation Programme. It provides participants with the conceptual frameworks and practical tools needed to transform co-created solutions into innovation pathways with market and ecosystem relevance.

The session draws heavily from Lean Startup principles, promoting a mindset of experimentation, iteration, and evidence-based decision-making. By working with business modelling tools such as the Business Model Canvas (BMC), participants develop a more strategic understanding of how their solutions create value for users and society.

In addition, this session strengthens an active engagement with tools that facilitate strategic thinking, customer discovery, and impact modelling, participants build their capacity to lead or contribute to mission-driven innovation processes within academic and multi-stakeholder contexts.

Ultimately, this session supports the KALEIDOS goal of enabling research-based solutions to evolve into validated, user-focused and value-oriented innovation initiatives.

Objective

To equip participants with practical tools and mindsets from the Lean Startup methodology to turn their early concepts into validated, user-oriented business models. Participants explore their value proposition, key partners, customer segments, and revenue streams, testing the feasibility and relevance of their ideas in real-world ecosystems.

Target audience

- KALEIDOS participants working on early-stage innovation projects
- Researchers and professionals seeking to translate research outcomes into viable solutions
- Teams exploring entrepreneurial pathways or preparing for stakeholder engagement
- Individuals with limited experience in business modelling, market validation, or lean methodologies

Methodology and content

This session followed an applied and iterative learning approach grounded in the Lean Startup methodology. The training combined conceptual framing with guided exercises, enabling participants to analyse and improve their initial ideas by exploring impact potential, business modelling, and user validation strategies.

The session was structured around six interconnected blocks:

1. **Impact and mission definition**
Participants defined the broader mission behind their idea, linking it to societal or ecosystem-level challenges. They explored potential Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that would help measure progress and impact over time.
2. **Problem/Solution reframing**
Teams revisited and refined their problem statement and proposed solution to

ensure coherence with user needs and contextual realities. Emphasis was placed on validating assumptions rather than assuming fit.

3. **Mission-Driven business modelling**
Using the Business Model Canvas (BMC), participants mapped the key elements of their solution: value proposition, customer segments, channels, cost structure, revenue streams, key partners, and more. This process helped clarify strategic dimensions and identify unknowns.
4. **Leaps of faith identification**
Teams identified the core assumptions ("leaps of faith") on which their business model relied—particularly those related to user interest, behaviour, willingness to pay, or delivery feasibility. These were flagged as key areas for validation.
5. **Customer Discovery**
A brief introduction to customer discovery helped teams understand how to test their assumptions through real-world engagement. This included a walkthrough of good practices in user interviews, common pitfalls, and interpretation of qualitative feedback.
6. **Customer interview design**
Participants worked on drafting a first list of interview questions, designed to explore users' experiences, problems, and motivations—without leading or pitching the idea. The goal was to learn, not to sell.

Throughout the session, facilitators used real examples and guided teams with targeted questions. The structure encouraged a mindset of hypothesis testing, strategic listening, and solution iteration—key to developing innovation projects that are both impactful and viable.

Materials needed

To support the interactive and strategic nature of the session, the following materials were used:

- Business Model Canvas (BMC) – available in both printable and digital formats for team-based work.
- Mission & KPI templates – to help teams define their societal goal and indicators of success.
- Problem/Solution reframing worksheet – to revisit and refine the challenge-solution fit.
- Leaps of Faith map – for identifying and documenting key assumptions behind each business model.
- Customer Interview Guide – including sample structure and question design tips.
- Collaborative tools – such as sticky notes, flipcharts, markers (in-person); or digital whiteboards, shared documents, and breakout rooms (online).
- Presentation slides – providing visual cues, theoretical framing, and instructions for exercises.

All materials were designed for flexible use in both face-to-face and online settings, ensuring accessibility and smooth facilitation across contexts.

The [slides used in session 4](#) can be found on the KALEIDOS website.

Exercises for face-to-face and online sessions

This session was structured as a guided workshop combining conceptual explanation and interactive exercises, with full adaptability to both face-to-face and online environments. The goal was to support participants in translating early ideas into structured, testable innovation models.

1. **Mission & impact definition:** Participants articulated the mission behind their innovation and identified at least one Key Performance Indicator (KPI) to track its potential impact.

2. **Problem/Solution reframing:** Teams revisited their original problem statement and refined it through guided questions such as:

- "What assumptions are we making?"
- "What is the root user need we are addressing?"

3. **Business Model Canvas (BMC):** Each team filled in their BMC, section by section, including value proposition, customer segments, channels, and cost structure.

4. **Leaps of faith identification:** Participants identified and labelled the riskiest assumptions in their model—especially around desirability, viability, and feasibility.

5. **Customer Discovery interview design:** Participants created a list of open-ended questions to validate their assumptions through user interviews.

Each exercise ended with a short group reflection to consolidate learning and align on next steps. In both delivery formats, facilitators played an active role in prompting iteration, challenging assumptions, and supporting team alignment.

Outcomes of the session and skills and competences addressed

This session enabled participants to take a significant step forward in transforming their ideas into structured, testable innovation models. By applying Lean Startup tools and methods, they gained a deeper understanding of how their proposed solutions could create value in real-world contexts—and how to iteratively validate their assumptions.

Key outcomes

- Completion of the first version of a Business Model Canvas for each project.
- Clear definition of the project mission and its potential social impact, linked to measurable KPIs.
- Identification of core "leaps of faith", highlighting which assumptions required validation.
- Drafting of a first customer interview guide, focused on learning from users rather than pitching.

- Strengthened understanding of the importance of testing and iteration in early-stage innovation.

Skills and Competences Addressed

This session directly contributed to the development of several cross-cutting and role-specific competences identified in the KALEIDOS D1.1 Analysis and Portfolio of Professional Skills and Competences for Open Science, including:

- **Strategic thinking** - Participants learned to align innovation efforts with mission, market needs, and value creation, using tools like the Business Model Canvas and Mission/KPI alignment.
- **Critical thinking** - The Lean approach required ongoing questioning and refinement of assumptions through customer discovery and problem-solution fit analysis.
- **Decision making** - Teams had to prioritise features, pivot strategies, and interpret customer feedback to guide their innovation pathway.
- **Systemic thinking** - The session encouraged understanding innovation not as isolated development, but embedded in complex user, funding, and institutional ecosystems.
- **Interact professionally** - Participants developed their ability to communicate and collaborate with diverse stakeholders during interviews and iterative feedback processes.
- **Increase impact of science on policy and society** - Lean startup tools helped participants focus their projects on measurable value, real-world outcomes, and sustainable change.
- **Mobilise resources** - Teams considered cost structures, partnerships, and investment needs—laying the groundwork for realistic implementation strategies.

This session reinforced participants' capacity to move from creative ideation to practical experimentation, laying the groundwork for further development and implementation of Open Science-based innovations.

A.5 Open Science and Knowledge Valorisation

Background and context

This session anchors the KALEIDOS training programme in the broader policy frameworks of Open Science (UNESCO) and Knowledge Valorisation (EU). It addresses the urgent need to move beyond traditional research valorisation models by embracing more inclusive, sustainable, and socially oriented pathways for transforming scientific knowledge into impact.

Objective

To raise awareness and provide practical understanding of Open Science and Knowledge Valorisation as strategic frameworks for increasing the societal, environmental and economic impact of research. The session introduces guiding principles, policy trends, and practical pathways for co-creating value beyond academia.

Target audience

- Researchers, innovation professionals, and project leaders
- Staff from knowledge transfer or technology transfer offices (KTO/TTO), policy units, and R&I services
- KALEIDOS participants exploring how to embed Open Science and impact in their projects

Methodology and content

The session followed a seminar and guided discussion format, with structured input followed by reflection and Q&A. Main topics included:

1. Open Science Foundations

- UNESCO's four pillars (open knowledge, infrastructure, societal engagement, dialogue with other systems)
- When and how Open Science principles apply throughout the research cycle (design, data, dissemination, impact)

2. EU Knowledge Valorisation Policy

- From dissemination to co-creation of social and economic value
- Valorisation beyond IP: open methods, policy impact, social innovation
- Stakeholder roles (academia, civil society, public authorities, industry)

3. Skills and incentives

- What competences researchers and institutions need (based on D1.1)
- Relevance of career assessment reform and responsible research metrics
- Institutional strategies and individual practices to enable valorisation

4. Cases and practices

- Examples of collaborative valorisation: CHC Labs, PP Labs, ageing deal pilots
- Tools: OpenAIRE, EOSC, impact KPIs, co-creation roadmaps

The session closed with an open discussion on participants' own barriers and opportunities in adopting these frameworks.

Materials needed

- Presentation slides covering Open Science and Knowledge Valorisation frameworks. The [slides used in session 5](#) can be found on the KALEIDOS website.
- Policy brief summaries

- Case study handouts or digital boards
- Reflection worksheets or online polls (for engagement)
- Recording tools or note templates for group sharing

All materials were suitable for both online and in-person formats.

Exercises for face-to-face and online sessions

Despite its seminar format, several interactive components were integrated:

- Guided Reflection Prompts: “Where does my current project align with Open Science principles?”
- Barrier Identification: Discussion of institutional and systemic blockers

Outcomes of the session and skills and competences addressed

This session helped participants shift from a traditional, linear view of research dissemination toward a broader, more strategic understanding of Open Science and Knowledge Valorisation as ongoing, multidirectional processes. By examining real cases, policy frameworks, and ethical considerations, participants were equipped to rethink how their research can generate value for diverse stakeholders.

Key Outcomes

- Clearer understanding of Open Science as a comprehensive framework for research transparency, collaboration, and societal engagement.
- Increased awareness of the diversity of valorisation pathways—including non-commercial, policy-driven, and social innovation strategies.
- Identification of enablers and barriers at both institutional and personal levels for implementing Open Science and impact practices.
- Inspiration to incorporate impact planning and stakeholder collaboration into participants' own research or innovation projects.

Skills and competences addressed

The session supported the development of key transversal and thematic competences from the KALEIDOS D1.1 skills portfolio, including:

- **Promote open access publications** - Emphasis was placed on making research outputs openly accessible to maximize visibility and reuse.
- **Promote the transfer of knowledge** - Participants examined strategies for translating research into practical, socially valuable applications.
- **Apply research ethics and integrity principles** - Core ethical principles and integrity standards were addressed in the context of open, responsible innovation.
- **Manage research data** - The session introduced good practices in data management aligned with FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).
- **Communicate to the broad public** - Techniques for adapting scientific messages to non-specialist audiences were presented as part of inclusive knowledge valorisation.

- **Increase impact of science on policy and society** - Participants reflected on how to align research valorisation with social needs and public policy goals, as the overarching focus was on enhancing the societal and economic impact of research beyond academia.
- **Critical thinking** - Encouraged analysis of traditional knowledge transfer models and their transformation under Open Science paradigms.
- **Strategic thinking** - Development of long-term strategies to ensure societal relevance and sustainability of research outcomes.
- **Valuing sustainability** - The session promoted alignment of innovation practices with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).
- **Interact professionally** - Discussion included ways to collaborate effectively with stakeholders from the quadruple helix ecosystem.
- **Systemic thinking** - Participants were encouraged to adopt a holistic view of knowledge ecosystems and interdependent innovation processes.

The session contributed to preparing participants to become agents of responsible and impactful research, aligned with the evolving policy landscape and institutional transformation toward Open Science.

A.6 Intellectual property

Background and context

This session deepens the KALEIDOS innovation training journey by addressing a critical and often underestimated component of knowledge valorisation: intellectual property (IP). It equips participants with practical strategies to identify, protect, and manage the outputs of research and innovation activities, ensuring that ideas can evolve into assets with societal and economic value.

Objective

To provide participants with essential knowledge on how to identify, protect, manage, and exploit intellectual property rights in research and innovation, both individually and in collaborative settings.

Target audience

- Researchers, innovators and technology developers
- Project coordinators and research managers
- Teams participating in KALEIDOS with innovation-oriented outputs
- TTO/KTO professionals and early-career entrepreneurs

Methodology and content

This session was delivered in the format of an expert-led seminar, combining theoretical foundations with practical guidance. The structure aimed to provide researchers and innovation professionals with a comprehensive understanding of how to protect and manage intellectual property (IP) in alignment with real-world research and innovation practices.

The content was organised around four key thematic blocks:

1. **Ways to protect R&D+I projects**

Participants were introduced to the main categories of intellectual property rights (IPR) relevant to research, development, and innovation:

- Patents and utility models for technical inventions
- Trademarks and industrial designs for branding and visual identity
- Copyright and trade secrets for software, data, and know-how
- Comparative examples were provided to clarify what type of protection applies in each case.

2. **The roadmap to protecting innovations**

The trainer outlined the typical IP protection process, from the early stages of idea development to national and international protection:

- Prior art and novelty search
- Filing strategies at national (OEPM), European (EPO, EUIPO), and global (WIPO) levels
- Freedom to Operate (FTO) analysis to prevent infringement risks
- Timing, costs, and alignment with the project's exploitation plan

3. **Procedures and tools to manage and protect IP**

Emphasis was placed on practical tools that support IP strategy in academic and collaborative environments:

- Non-Disclosure Agreements (NDAs) and Memorandums of Understanding (MoUs)
- Templates for licensing and joint ownership
- Internal protocols for safeguarding know-how and publication timing
- Use of digital proof-of-authorship tools such as blockchain or timestamping

4. **The role of IP in collaborative projects**

The session closed with a discussion on how to manage IP in multi-partner settings, such as EU-funded projects or public-private collaborations:

- Shared ownership and exploitation clauses
- Open innovation models vs closed proprietary approaches
- Risk mitigation in interdisciplinary and cross-sectoral teams
- Institutional roles and support mechanisms (e.g. TTOs, legal offices)

This structured methodology provided participants with the clarity, tools, and confidence to start applying IP protection strategies to their own innovations—both within the KALEIDOS framework and beyond.

Materials needed

To support the seminar and facilitate a practical understanding of intellectual property management, the following materials were provided:

- Presentation slides summarising key concepts, legal frameworks, and real-world examples related to IP protection
- Visual charts detailing the main types of intellectual property, their scope, duration, and eligibility criteria
- Case study summaries, used to prompt discussion around typical IP challenges in research and innovation settings
- Access to public IP databases (e.g. Espacenet, EUIPO, OEPM, WIPO), enabling participants to explore patents, trademarks, and prior art

All materials were designed to be fully adaptable for both face-to-face and online delivery, ensuring inclusive and flexible participation across formats. The [slides used in session 6](#) can be found on the KALEIDOS website.

Exercises for face-to-face and online sessions

Given the specialized and intensive nature of the session, no structured exercises were carried out. The session was designed as an informative seminar, focused on the transmission of key concepts, legal frameworks and good practices related to intellectual property in research and innovation contexts.

Outcomes of the session and skills and competences addressed

This session provided participants with a solid foundational understanding of intellectual property (IP) as a key component of responsible innovation and knowledge valorisation. Through expert-led input and real case examples, participants gained clarity on the tools, procedures, and considerations needed to protect research-based outcomes effectively and ethically.

Key outcomes

- Improved awareness of the main types of intellectual property and their relevance to different innovation outputs
- Understanding of the roadmap for protecting innovation at national, European, and international levels
- Insight into risks and responsibilities related to disclosure, ownership, and collaborative project management
- Practical orientation towards engaging with institutional support structures (e.g. TTOs, legal offices)

Skills and competences addressed

The session contributed to several transversal and role-specific skills outlined in the D1.1 portfolio, including:

- **Promote the transfer of knowledge** - The session focused on mechanisms to protect and manage results in ways that enable transfer to other sectors and applications.
- **Apply research ethics and integrity principles** - Ethical considerations around ownership, authorship, and responsible protection of results were discussed.

- **Manage research data** - Participants learned how data protection relates to IP and how to manage it accordingly, including issues of confidentiality and licensing.
- **Increase impact of science on policy and society** - Intellectual property was framed as a lever for amplifying the real-world impact of innovation by enabling exploitation and application.
- **Strategic thinking** - Participants were encouraged to consider IP protection as part of a broader innovation and valorisation strategy.
- **Critical thinking** - The session promoted an analytical view of when, how, and why to protect intellectual assets in alignment with open innovation principles.
- **Interact professionally** - Participants reflected on roles and responsibilities when working with legal and tech transfer offices, collaborators, or industry partners.
- **Decision making** - Choosing the appropriate IP pathway (e.g. patent, copyright, design rights) requires contextual, informed decisions aligned with project goals.
- **Practical insights** - The session focused on real-life scenarios and institutional procedures to equip researchers with applied knowledge of IP.
- **Mobilise resources** - IP was connected to resource generation through licensing, spin-offs, or collaborative agreements.

Overall, the session reinforced the ability of participants to act as informed, proactive agents in the responsible protection and exploitation of research results, in alignment with Open Science and mission-driven innovation goals.

A.7 Digital resources to create high-impact visual presentations for your projects & elevator pitch training

Background and context

This session addressed a key cross-cutting need in knowledge valorization: the ability to effectively communicate research-based innovation. A high-impact visual or presentation is not only a dissemination tool, but is often the gateway to obtaining funding, collaborations or support from stakeholders.

Objective

To enhance participants' skills in structuring, designing, and delivering compelling presentations and elevator pitches. The session aimed to boost confidence and clarity when communicating innovation projects to diverse audiences.

Target audience

- Researchers and project teams

- Early-stage innovators preparing to pitch their solutions
- Individuals seeking to improve visual storytelling and public speaking for valorisation purposes

Methodology and content

The session followed a practical and structured approach, guiding participants through the foundations of high-impact communication and the tools needed to present their projects effectively to diverse audiences. The methodology combined conceptual input, examples, and a brief hands-on exercise.

The session was structured around the following components:

1. **Introduction to high-impact presentations**

Participants were invited to reflect on the importance of strategic communication in research valorisation. The speaker introduced key principles such as storytelling, visual coherence, and user-centred design.

2. **Elevator pitch structure**

A 30–90 second pitch format was presented, including 5 essential blocks:

- The problem or opportunity
- The proposed solution
- Market and early adopters
- Business model
- Call to action

3. **Pitch deck design and presentation flow**

A recommended 10–12 slide structure for full presentations was introduced, especially for more mature or investor-ready projects. Content included branding, market size, value proposition, competitive advantage, team, and financials.

4. **Examples**

Participants analysed real examples—including TED talks, startup pitches and design-led corporate presentations (e.g. Apple, Meta)—to identify good practices and common pitfalls.

5. **Design tools & visual resources (hands-on block).**

The final section offered a tour of digital tools for designing impactful presentations

The approach balanced theoretical framing and practical application, helping participants develop stronger communication skills tailored to innovation contexts.

Materials needed

To support the training and enable practical exploration of visual communication tools, the following materials were provided:

- Presentation slides with structured guidance on pitch formats, slide content, and visual storytelling strategies
- Templates for elevator pitch drafting, including the 5-block model (problem, solution, audience, model, CTA)

- Recommended pitch deck outline for advanced presentations (10–12 slides)
- Links to online design tools:
 - Basic tools: PowerPoint, Canva
 - Intermediate tools: Adobe Illustrator, InDesign
 - Complementary platforms: Giphy, Flaticon, Pexels, Renderforest, Adobe Express, Dafont
- Visual inspiration resources, including video examples, TED talks, and branding examples (e.g. Apple, Meta)

All materials were accessible and adaptable for both online and face-to-face formats, allowing participants to engage with them during or after the session depending on the available time and delivery mode. The [slides used in session 7](#) can be found on the KALEIDOS website.

Exercises for face-to-face and online sessions

This session was primarily delivered as an informative and inspirational seminar. As such, no formal exercises were conducted. The focus was on conceptual input, demonstration of examples, and presentation of tools that participants could explore independently.

Interaction was encouraged through:

- Live Q&A moments
- Group reflection prompts on participants' own pitch challenges
- Demonstrations of tools (e.g. Canva, Renderforest) for future use

This format was designed to provide practical inspiration rather than hands-on training, allowing participants to apply the content at their own pace in subsequent stages of their projects.

Outcomes of the session and skills and competences addressed

This session enabled participants to strengthen their ability to communicate complex innovation projects clearly, persuasively, and visually—an essential competence for increasing the impact and visibility of research-based initiatives. By presenting structured formats and accessible tools, the session laid the groundwork for participants to independently develop effective elevator pitches and project presentations.

Key Outcomes

- Improved understanding of how to structure and deliver a compelling elevator pitch
- Familiarity with the standard components of an effective pitch deck
- Awareness of accessible digital tools to support visual storytelling and brand identity
- Increased confidence in preparing communication materials for funders, partners, and public audiences

Skills and competences addressed

The session contributed to several transversal competences identified in the KALEIDOS D1.1 Portfolio of Skills for Open Science, including:

- **Communicate to the broad public** - The session focused on making complex research ideas accessible, persuasive, and relevant to non-specialist audiences. The session strengthened the ability to use visual elements effectively to support clarity, engagement, and message retention. Through elevator pitch training, participants improved their confidence, structure, and delivery in presenting innovation projects.
- **Strategic thinking** - Participants were trained to align their communication strategy with project goals, target audience, and broader impact objectives.
- **Interact professionally** - Crafting a compelling pitch requires adapting tone, content, and language to various professional audiences (e.g. funders, partners, public).
- **Increase impact of science on policy and society** - The focus on messaging and storytelling reinforced the importance of clearly articulating the societal value of research.
- **Critical thinking** - Participants learned to filter and prioritise information, and to anticipate audience reactions and questions.
- **Adaptability** - Visual communication and pitch formats were tailored to different channels and delivery modes (slides, oral, online, face-to-face).

Together, these skills support participants' roles as proactive agents of Open Science and valorisation, capable of mobilising attention and action around their innovations.

A.8 Communication to general public

Background and context

This session addresses the growing need for researchers and innovators to communicate their work clearly and meaningfully to non-specialist audiences. As part of the KALEIDOS training programme, it reinforces the idea that societal impact depends not only on producing knowledge, but also on ensuring it reaches and resonates with the wider public.

Objective

To equip participants with the awareness and guidance necessary to communicate their research and innovation projects to the public in clear, accessible, and engaging ways. The session aimed to help participants define their audiences, shape their messages, and choose appropriate channels for impact.

Target audience

- Researchers, early-career academics, and innovation professionals
- Project teams preparing for public dissemination and stakeholder engagement
- Participants of programme seeking to increase the social visibility and relevance of their work

Methodology and content

The session was delivered as a conceptual and reflective training, designed to foster awareness of how communication to general audiences contributes to societal impact. Rather than offering technical tools, it provided a strategic framework to guide participants in thinking critically about how they communicate their research and innovation.

Key components of the session included:

- **The purpose of public communication:** Clarifying how it differs from academic dissemination and why it matters in the context of Open Science and knowledge valorisation
- **Audience identification:** Encouraging participants to reflect on who they want to reach (e.g. citizens, policymakers, civil society organisations) and what those audiences value
- **Message framing:** How to transform complex scientific content into clear, relevant, and emotionally engaging narratives
- **Channel strategy:** Exploring the pros and cons of formats such as social media, newsletters, podcasts, infographics, videos, and public events
- **Planning and alignment:** Highlighting how communication efforts should align with project milestones, funding requirements, and stakeholder engagement strategies
- **Engagement as a two-way process:** Emphasising dialogue, listening, and co-creation rather than one-way broadcasting

The session was supported by examples of real communication materials, reflection prompts, and guiding questions to help participants apply the concepts to their own contexts.

Materials needed

- Presentation slides with definitions, strategies, and guiding questions. The [slides used in session 8](#) can be found on the KALEIDOS website.
- Examples of communication formats (e.g. tweets, infographics, public talks)
- Optional tools for assessing communication impact (e.g. feedback forms, analytics dashboards)

All materials were adaptable for both face-to-face and online delivery.

Exercises for face-to-face and online sessions

This was a mainly conceptual session. However, participants were encouraged to reflect individually or in small groups on the following questions:

- Who is your audience?
- What do you want them to know, feel, or do?
- How can you make your message accessible and engaging?
- What channel is most appropriate for your content and audience?

These reflective prompts aimed to stimulate awareness and inspire participants to develop tailored communication strategies for their projects.

Outcomes of the session and skills and competences addressed

This session increased participants' awareness of the strategic role public communication plays in the valorisation of research and innovation. It helped them understand how to identify target audiences, craft accessible and engaging messages, and choose appropriate channels to reach broader societal groups.

Key Outcomes

- Recognition of public communication as an essential component of Open Science and responsible research practices
- Enhanced ability to differentiate between dissemination, communication, and engagement
- Greater clarity on how to frame key messages and align them with audience needs
- Inspiration to apply strategic communication principles in participants' ongoing and future projects

Skills and competences addressed

The session supported the development of several transversal and Open Science-related competences identified in the D1.1 portfolio, including:

- **Communicate to the broad public** - This was the session's core objective: to train participants in making science understandable, relevant, and engaging for non-expert audiences.
- **Promote the transfer of knowledge** - By learning to communicate beyond academia, participants advanced the potential for their research to be taken up and used by society.
- **Increase impact of science on policy and society** - The ability to connect with general audiences enhances the reach and societal influence of research.
- **Strategic thinking** - Participants had to frame their messages with purpose and intention, choosing formats and channels appropriate to their communication goals.
- **Critical thinking** - Emphasis was placed on selecting, simplifying, and shaping content in ways that preserve meaning without losing rigour.
- **Empathy** - Understanding audience needs, prior knowledge, and perspectives was key to crafting accessible narratives.
- **Interact professionally** - Researchers practiced interacting with journalists, media professionals, and the public, adapting language and behaviour to context.
- **Adaptability** - Participants learned to adapt messages and formats to different audiences (e.g. youth, policy makers, media).
- **Manage learning** - They also developed awareness of how to use communication moments as opportunities for mutual learning between researchers and society.

By reinforcing these competences, the session empowered participants to act as ambassadors of responsible science, capable of building bridges between research and society.

A.9 Resources and financial challenges

Background and context

Securing funding and managing resources are critical steps in the knowledge valorisation process. This session equips researchers and innovators with a strategic overview of the financial landscape surrounding research and innovation (R&I), helping them navigate available mechanisms and anticipate the structural and regulatory challenges.

Objective

To familiarise participants with the financial mechanisms available to support R&I activities and innovation-driven projects. The session aimed to help them understand the funding landscape, anticipate common administrative challenges, and build a strategic mindset towards resource planning and proposal development.

Target audience

- Early-stage researchers and innovation teams
- Project managers and coordinators of R&I projects
- Professionals seeking to scale up innovation projects through public or private funding

Methodology and content

The session followed a structured and informative seminar format, aimed at providing participants with a strategic overview of funding and resource management for innovation and research valorisation. It combined expert input, conceptual explanations, and guided reflection on real institutional challenges.

The content was organised into four interrelated blocks:

1. **Funding landscape mapping**

Participants were introduced to the main types of funding sources, including public (e.g. Horizon Europe, national and regional programmes), private (e.g. foundations, venture capital, crowdfunding), and hybrid mechanisms. The importance of matching each funding type to the maturity of the innovation was emphasised.

2. **Financial instruments and pathways**

The session outlined different funding modalities—grants, loans, equity, prizes—and explained their implications in terms of risk, return, and control.

Participants learned about project lifecycles, call calendars, and the dynamics of competitive funding.

3. **Administrative and legal considerations**

The trainer presented typical bureaucratic barriers and regulatory requirements, such as eligibility criteria, grant agreements, reporting obligations, and institutional overheads. The role of support offices (e.g. TTOs, grants offices) was highlighted as essential to success.

4. **Strategic planning for resource readiness**

The session concluded with practical advice on long-term funding strategies, including how to build a funding roadmap aligned with Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs), anticipate resource gaps, and combine instruments for different project stages.

The methodology encouraged participants to reflect on their own projects and institutions, fostering awareness of funding ecosystems and the ability to act strategically within them.

Materials needed

- Presentation slides with funding landscapes, process timelines, and financial strategy templates. The [slides used during session 9](#) can be found on the KALEIDOS website.
- Links to EU funding portals (e.g. Horizon Europe, EIC), national fund directories, and private investment sources
- Diagrams illustrating funding types, project stages, and administrative procedures
- Recommended readings on innovation financing and proposal preparation

All materials were compatible with face-to-face and online formats.

Exercises for face-to-face and online sessions

No structured exercises were conducted, but participants were invited to reflect on:

- What funding options align with their current project stage?
- What administrative or regulatory barriers have they encountered before?
- How could they build a balanced, long-term funding strategy?

This reflective approach encouraged personal mapping of needs and readiness.

Outcomes of the session and skills and competences addressed

This session provided participants with a structured understanding of the financial ecosystem that supports research and innovation projects. By mapping funding sources, financial instruments, and administrative processes, it empowered participants to make informed decisions about funding strategy, resource mobilisation, and institutional coordination.

Key Outcomes

- Clear overview of available public, private, and hybrid funding mechanisms, and their suitability across innovation stages
- Increased awareness of regulatory, administrative, and operational constraints linked to resource management in R&I projects
- Enhanced ability to plan funding strategically, linking project maturity with appropriate instruments and support structures
- Recognition of the role of institutional offices (e.g. TTOs, research services) in enabling successful financing

Skills and Competences Addressed

The session reinforced several key competences described in the D1.1 KALEIDOS portfolio, including:

- **Mobilise resources** - Central to the session, participants explored how to identify, secure, and manage financial and non-financial resources for innovation projects.
- **Strategic thinking** - The session guided participants in aligning resource strategies with project goals, innovation roadmaps, and impact missions.
- **Decision making** - Participants had to analyse funding opportunities, prioritise financial needs, and assess risks and sustainability.
- **Promote the transfer of knowledge** - Understanding resource mobilisation enables researchers to move ideas beyond the lab into real-world application and use.
- **Increase impact of science on policy and society** - Effective resource planning supports scaling and sustainability of research-based innovations with public value.
- **Systemic thinking** - Participants considered how their projects fit within larger innovation and funding ecosystems, including regional, national, and EU-level instruments.
- **Interact professionally** - The session included how to engage with funders, partners, and support institutions in a clear and credible manner.
- **Valuing sustainability** - Financial strategies were developed with long-term viability and responsible resource use in mind.
- **Practical insights** - The session provided hands-on knowledge about grant design, budgeting, and support structures, building applied financial literacy.

Through this session, participants gained tools and insights to navigate the complex financing environment surrounding knowledge valorisation and innovation within the Open Science paradigm.

A.10 Mentoring

Background and context

The mentoring phase is a critical element of the KALEIDOS training programme, offering personalised guidance to support the progression of innovation projects

beyond the group sessions. It represents a practical application of the co-creation, valorisation, and Open Science principles introduced throughout the previous modules.

Objective

To provide tailored mentoring to project teams, helping them refine their proposals, overcome challenges, and prepare for further development, communication, or funding. The goal is to bridge the gap between ideation and implementation through personalised expert guidance.

Target audience

- Project teams who participated in ideation and training sessions
- Researchers and innovation professionals seeking validation and feedback

Methodology and content

The mentoring phase was designed as a personalised and project-oriented support process, complementing the structured training previously delivered in the KALEIDOS programme. It offered each team the opportunity to receive tailored guidance from experienced mentors, with the objective of refining their innovation proposals and preparing for the next stage of development.

The methodology was based on small team mentoring sessions, either in person or online, and adapted to the maturity level, sector, and specific challenges of each project. Key components included:

- **Project review:** Mentors revisited the project ideas developed during the ideation sessions, assessing coherence, user orientation, and impact potential
- **Strategic guidance:** Participants received advice on critical aspects such as prototyping, stakeholder alignment, communication strategy, or business modelling
- **Challenge navigation:** Mentors supported teams in identifying current bottlenecks and exploring feasible next steps
- **Validation and feedback:** Constructive critique helped teams test their assumptions and strengthen their value propositions
- **Action planning:** Mentors assisted participants in designing short- and medium-term roadmaps for development, engagement, or funding

The approach promoted deep reflection, encouraged strategic refinement, and supported participants in consolidating the knowledge acquired throughout the KALEIDOS training modules.

○ Materials needed

To ensure effective mentoring sessions, the following materials were used or recommended:

- Project summaries or “Initial Project Folders” developed in previous KALEIDOS sessions
- Mentor briefing documents, including background information on each team’s progress, objectives, and specific needs
- Mentoring guide, outlining the purpose, scope, and structure of the mentoring process.
- Mentoring session templates to support note-taking, action planning, and follow-up documentation.

These resources ensured that both mentors and mentees were well-prepared and aligned, facilitating productive and context-specific dialogue.

The [mentoring guide](#) and the [mentoring follow-up form](#) used during the KALEIDOS Ideas Generation Programme can be found on the KALEIDOS website.

Outcomes of the session and skills and competences addressed

The mentoring sessions played a key role in consolidating and personalising the learning process initiated through the KALEIDOS training programme. They provided tailored guidance that enabled participants to refine their innovation concepts, address practical challenges, and define clear paths forward based on their project’s maturity and ecosystem fit.

Key outcomes

- Enhanced clarity and focus in project articulation, aligned with user needs and ecosystem conditions
- Personalised feedback and external validation of ideas, strengthening the feasibility and relevance of each proposal
- Development of tailored action plans for future steps, including prototyping, funding, communication, or stakeholder engagement
- Increased confidence and decision-making capacity among participants

Skills and competences addressed

The session supported the development of several core competences from the D1.1 portfolio:

- **Interact professionally** - Participants engaged in structured mentoring sessions, learning to communicate needs, receive guidance, and engage in peer learning respectfully and effectively.
- **Strategic thinking** - Through mentor feedback, participants refined their project plans, aligning innovation strategies with real-world expectations and feasibility.
- **Manage learning** - The mentoring process encouraged self-reflection, active listening, and integration of new knowledge into ongoing project development.
- **Decision making** - Mentors helped participants navigate choices, challenges, and priorities, enhancing their ability to make informed and timely decisions.
- **Critical thinking** - Mentor input challenged assumptions, pushing teams to reassess project focus, user needs, or technical feasibility.
- **Empathy** - Mentoring fostered mutual understanding and encouraged participants to incorporate diverse perspectives and feedback into their work.

- **Promote open innovation** - Mentors often encouraged broader collaboration, interdisciplinarity, and openness in problem-solving approaches.
- **Self-regulation** - Participants managed feedback constructively, adjusted expectations, and regulated emotional responses throughout the iteration process.
- **Mobilise resources** - Guidance on funding, partnerships, and institutional navigation helped teams build realistic plans for resource acquisition.

This final component of the programme helped participants internalise a more mature, mission-oriented, and impact-driven approach to innovation within the Open Science framework.

A.11 Prototyping

Background and context

Prototyping is a key step in the knowledge valorisation process, bridging the gap between abstract ideas and tangible innovations. This session introduced participants to prototyping as a means of early validation, iterative improvement, and communication of value. With support from an external expert, teams explored how to visualise their concepts and make them testable and shareable.

Objective

To introduce participants to fundamental prototyping methods and support them in transforming their innovation ideas into tangible or visual representations. The process aimed to improve the feasibility, user orientation, and communicability of their projects by guiding teams through the early stages of prototype design with the tailored input of an external expert.

Target audience

- Project teams that have participated in ideation and mentoring sessions
- Early-stage innovators seeking to move from concept to testable format
- Researchers and professionals interested in visualising and validating their ideas

Methodology and content

This module was implemented through a series of practical sessions focused on transforming project ideas into tangible, visual, or interactive prototypes. Guided by an external expert in innovation and design, participants engaged in an iterative process of creation, testing, and refinement.

The methodology combined:

- **Expert-led collective sessions:**
These sessions introduced key principles of prototyping, showcased examples of different formats (e.g. sketches, wireframes, mock-ups, storyboards), and provided guidance on how to choose the most appropriate approach depending on the nature of each project.
- **Individualised team work sessions:**
Each project team received tailored support from the expert to develop their prototype based on their concept, goals, and maturity level. This included feedback rounds, visual coaching, and discussions on how to best express their solution's value and usability.
- **Iterative refinement:**
Across multiple sessions, teams improved their prototypes by integrating feedback, exploring new visual strategies, and preparing for future communication or validation with stakeholders.

This blended methodology ensured that all teams progressed at their own pace while benefiting from expert insights and a structured approach to prototyping as a core step in the innovation journey.

Outcomes of the session and skills and competences addressed

Key Outcomes:

- Each team developed a tangible or visual prototype of their project
- Increased capacity to communicate the concept to stakeholders, funders, or users
- Improved problem-solution alignment and refinement of the value proposition through expert feedback

Skills and competences addressed:

- **Creativity** - Participants transformed abstract ideas into visual or functional prototypes, requiring imaginative thinking and experimentation.
- **Strategic thinking** - Prototyping helped teams define priorities, align features with user needs, and clarify the core mission of their innovation.
- **Critical thinking** - Teams continuously evaluated feasibility, utility, and relevance while building initial versions of their solutions.
- **Interact professionally** - Participants collaborated with an expert mentor and peers, articulating ideas, giving/receiving feedback, and improving outcomes.
- **Practical insights** - Through iterative exercises, teams gained hands-on understanding of translating concepts into usable formats (e.g. sketches, mock-ups, user flows).
- **Systemic thinking** - The session encouraged thinking beyond the prototype: integration into the ecosystem, user adoption, and pathways to implementation.
- **Adaptability** - Teams responded flexibly to mentor suggestions, design challenges, and technological or resource constraints.
- **Promote open innovation** - Prototyping was positioned as a collaborative and testable stage that invites co-creation with users and stakeholders.
- **Decision making** - Participants selected what to prototype, what tools to use, and how to communicate their solution's value.

- **Work in teams** – Participants worked in teams to develop the prototype

The session marked a transition from idea development to tangible project articulation, reinforcing KALEIDOS' mission to bridge Open Science and innovation impact.

A.12 Final presentation simulation

Background and context

The ability to communicate research-based innovation clearly and convincingly is essential for valorisation, stakeholder engagement, and access to funding. This simulation session was designed to prepare participants for their final pitch presentations by offering a realistic and structured rehearsal.

Objective

To simulate final pitch presentations in a realistic setting and provide constructive feedback to help participants refine their delivery, storytelling, and visual communication. The session aimed to increase participants' confidence, clarity, and strategic messaging ahead of external presentations.

Target audience

- KALEIDOS participants preparing to present their innovation projects
- Teams aiming to pitch to funders, institutions, or stakeholders
- Researchers seeking to improve their presentation and public engagement skills

Methodology and content

The session was structured as a simulated pitch event, allowing participants to rehearse their final presentations under realistic conditions. Each team was invited to present their innovation project using their visual materials and prototype elements, within a set time limit (5 to 7 minutes), simulating the dynamics of professional evaluation or public pitching events.

The structure of the session included:

- Live team presentations, focusing on key elements: problem statement, solution, value proposition, user need, implementation strategy, and expected impact
- Peer and facilitator feedback rounds, offering constructive critique on delivery, storytelling, slide design, and clarity of the message

- Q&A segments, where other participants could ask questions or request clarification, emulating real pitch panel dynamics
- Group reflection and improvement tips, highlighting common strengths and areas for refinement, useful for both presenters and observers

The session encouraged self-evaluation, audience awareness, and the application of strategic communication principles introduced in previous training modules. It also served to boost participants' confidence and polish their final message before presenting in external settings.

Materials needed

- Final presentation slides and visual supports (e.g. pitch deck, prototype visuals)
- Timer or countdown tools (digital or physical) to manage presentation length
- Feedback forms or structured templates for peer and facilitator comments
- Presentation space or online platform with screen-sharing capabilities

All materials and formats were suitable for both online and face-to-face delivery.

Exercises for face-to-face and online sessions

The entire session was an interactive exercise:

- Face-to-face: Participants pitched live in front of the group, using projection tools and physical gestures
- Online: Teams shared their screens and presented live in a video call, simulating a virtual event

Feedback was given followed each pitch

The exercise encouraged self-awareness, iterative improvement, and peer learning.

Outcomes of the session and skills and competences addressed

This session provided participants with the opportunity to simulate the final presentation of their innovation projects. By rehearsing in a realistic, time-constrained, and feedback-oriented environment, participants refined their storytelling abilities, strengthened their confidence, and enhanced the clarity, persuasiveness, and impact of their message.

Key Outcomes

- Improved structure, timing, and narrative flow in innovation pitches
- Increased ability to communicate complex ideas clearly and persuasively to non-specialist audiences
- Better alignment between project content, visual support, and delivery style
- Heightened awareness of audience engagement strategies and messaging coherence

- Valuable feedback from peers and facilitators integrated into final versions of each pitch

Skills and competences addressed

The session contributed to the development of multiple transversal and role-specific competences identified in the KALEIDOS D1.1 portfolio:

- **Communicate to the broad public** - Participants practiced conveying their research-based innovation clearly and compellingly to non-specialist audiences. The simulation strengthened participants' delivery, timing, body language, and persuasive communication in a realistic setting. Visual materials were refined to support clarity, coherence, and emotional connection with the audience.
- **Strategic thinking** - Teams refined their pitches to highlight value propositions, project impact, and alignment with target stakeholder needs.
- **Interact professionally** - The session simulated real-world evaluation dynamics, requiring respectful engagement, listening, and feedback response.
- **Critical thinking** - Participants improved content structure by selecting and emphasising the most relevant and impactful messages.
- **Increase impact of science on policy and society** - Participants worked on clearly articulating the social, scientific, and economic relevance of their projects.
- **Adaptability** - Teams adjusted their messages in response to timing constraints, feedback, and the context of the simulated pitch.

By the end of the session, participants were equipped to confidently present their projects in real-world contexts—whether to funders, stakeholders, or the broader public—supporting KALEIDOS' mission to foster responsible, impactful science communication and innovation.

A.13 Final event

Background and context

The Final Event marked the culmination of the KALEIDOS training programme, offering participants the opportunity to present their innovation projects to an external expert advisor. This session served as a focused feedback opportunity rather than a public dissemination event.

Objective

To provide participants with the opportunity to deliver their final project presentations to an external expert, simulating a real-world evaluation context. The session aimed to help teams refine their communication, receive targeted feedback, and strengthen their readiness for future stakeholder engagement, funding applications, or public dissemination.

Target audience

- KALEIDOS participant teams
- Programme mentors and facilitators
- External advisor (expert in innovation, technology transfer or entrepreneurship)

Methodology and content

The session was structured as a semi-formal internal pitch event, where each team delivered a time-bound presentation to the external advisor. The content included:

- A clear articulation of the problem, solution, and value proposition
- Description of the prototyping and development process
- Strategic elements: potential users, partners, funding pathways

Each presentation was followed by individualised feedback from the advisor, focused on:

- The clarity and coherence of the project
- Its feasibility and innovation potential
- The effectiveness of communication and strategic positioning

This format fostered confidence and critical awareness while simulating a real evaluation context.

Materials needed

- Final pitch presentations (slide decks, visual summaries, or mock-ups)
- Project documentation (e.g. value proposition, business model, or prototyping outputs)
- Timer or timekeeping tools for managing pitch duration
- Feedback templates or note-taking sheets for the external advisor
- Physical or digital setup (room with projector or online platform with screen sharing)

The [project executive summary template](#) can be found on the KALEIDOS website.

Exercises for face-to-face and online sessions

Although the session was structured as a final presentation rather than a training module, it included several interactive and evaluative components applicable in both formats:

- Live project presentations by each team, simulating a formal pitch scenario
- Expert feedback exchange, delivered in real time and adapted to each project

These elements promoted reflective learning, communication skills, and readiness for real-world evaluation settings.

Outcomes of the session and skills and competences addressed

This session provided a structured, feedback-oriented space for participants to finalise their innovation presentations and test their communication strategies with a qualified external advisor. It functioned as both a simulation and an evaluation opportunity, reinforcing participants' preparedness for real-world dissemination and funding contexts.

Key Outcomes

- Teams delivered a time-managed presentation of their innovation projects, summarising problem, solution, value proposition, and next steps
- Participants received personalised feedback from an external expert, highlighting strengths and areas for improvement
- Projects were further refined in terms of clarity, structure, and strategic alignment
- Participants strengthened their readiness for upcoming stakeholder interactions or institutional valorisation opportunities

Skills and Competences Addressed

This session contributed to the development of key competences as outlined in the D1.1 portfolio:

- **Communicate to the broad public** - Participants presented their final project pitches in a professional and accessible format to an external advisor, demonstrating clarity and engagement. Final pitches reinforced skills in confident delivery, time management, and persuasive communication. The presentations showcased refined use of slides, storytelling, and visual tools to support narrative coherence.
- **Promote the transfer of knowledge** - The final presentation served as a public valorisation moment, highlighting the potential for real-world application of research results.
- **Strategic thinking** - Teams articulated their vision, solution roadmap, and value proposition in alignment with societal and user needs.
- **Interact professionally** - Participants demonstrated their ability to respond to expert feedback, communicate with stakeholders, and engage in dialogue with an external evaluator.
- **Increase impact of science on policy and society** - The event required teams to highlight how their innovations respond to specific societal challenges and create measurable value.

The session marked the final stage of the KALEIDOS learning journey, consolidating the skills necessary for participants to act as innovation ambassadors within their academic and professional ecosystems.

CONCLUSION

Researchers and research managers—highlighted the value of the KALEIDOS Ideas Generation Programme as a powerful method to accelerate systemic change in research and innovation ecosystems. The process was particularly appreciated for its ability to work closely with territorial needs, starting from a deep understanding of local challenges through engagement with the ecosystem. This approach allowed participants to define problems more accurately and collaboratively, resulting in more targeted and feasible solutions.

The co-creation process at the heart of the programme was seen as a key element in advancing knowledge valorisation practices. However, participants also emphasised that such a process requires a significant investment of time and sustained engagement. Balancing this commitment with existing responsibilities—such as teaching, project management, and other academic tasks—proved challenging for many, underscoring the need for institutional support and appropriate resourcing.

Importantly, the challenge-driven methodology used in KALEIDOS was recognised as being aligned with other regional innovation practices, such as problem framing and mission-oriented approaches. This makes it a flexible and adaptable tool, suitable for different regional contexts and levels of maturity in Open Science and knowledge valorisation. A key strength identified by participants was the flexibility of the programme to develop the ideas: it did not impose a single method, but allowed researchers to compare, test, and selectively integrate new approaches into their own established models. This ensured higher relevance, ownership, and the likelihood of long-term adoption.

The experience confirmed that, with appropriate tailoring, the method can effectively support the development of context-specific strategies and foster long-term cultural change in support of knowledge valorisation and Open Science.

Finally, the whole KALEIDOS Ideas Generation Program allowed the participants to acquire and develop key Open Science skills, emphasizing on impact, systemic vision and collaboration (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Open Science skills acquired

ANNEX 1. RESEARCHERS' TEAMS

UAB

Challenge: How can we improve cities to create urban environments that promote active development and greater integration of older people in community life with the aim of improving their quality of life, ensuring their autonomy and fostering social inclusion?

Team: 4 researchers with expertise Psychiatry, Geography and Law.

Mentors: 2 mentors from the Public Administration and a Start-up

University of Lorraine:

Challenge: As digital technologies become integral to daily life, elderly individuals with less familiarity with cybersecurity are increasingly targeted by cyber threats such as scams, phishing, and identity theft. How can digital literacy programs, policy frameworks, and technological safeguards be designed to protect aging populations from cyber risks while ensuring their digital inclusion and adaptability?

Team: 6 researchers with expertise in Natural Language Processing and Knowledge Representation; Innovation Processes; AI-based decision support systems for sustainable infrastructure management; and Engineering

Mentor: Innovation engineering expert

Karlstad University

Challenge: Driven Research Framework for Digital Health & Aging. The Digital Health Network applies a challenge-driven approach to improve digital health for aging populations. Through the Quadruple Helix Model—engaging academia, industry, government, and civil society—it seeks to identify gaps, test solutions, and scale effective models.

Team: 6 researchers with expertise in Psychology, Research & Innovation

Mentors: 2 mentors from the private sector

University of Bologna

Challenge: How can we increase engagement between different stakeholders to ensure that resources are shared more effectively, leading to more activities and resources for the target community?

Team: 1 researcher in Digital Humanities

Mentor: Designer and social entrepreneur

